

CITATION METRIC AN APPLICATION TO $h/i-10$ INDEXES

By

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Abstract : In Research level statistics level like number of CITATIONS will improve Researcher's Credibility. But mathematically Citation = $f(h, i-10 \text{ index})$. h -index is generally equal to number of CITATIONS ie h - with a **total number of Research**

Publications i with a restriction that the maximum value of $h < = i$. The $i-10$ index = Number of CITATIONS ≥ 10 .

IMPRESSION: From my **Google Scholar profile** (pdf file attached herewith) Number of Publications = Number of CITATIONS = 2, ie h -index = 2 but $i-10$ index = 0 ie $i < = 10$.

REF:

1. JAYDIP DATTA, The effect of Normalisation on Partition Function - A Wave Particle Duality (UPDATED VERSION) , July 2020 , DOI: [10.6084/m9.figshare.12689792](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12689792).
(<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331951715> The effect of Normalisation on Partition Function - A Wave Particle Duality UPDATED VERSION? sg=E6w3XjGePOmMMNZRsBnKUErC-OzB9_bT28qk2X0Y9c3UJ7zqR0cokJchlMU0IveXR4klIn5NNg0Hppq6bnmgOwtCV2BUO2qVSnCWxBqZ.MAGLlcQBv65LO6oIZI_NBI3hzNA3lwGwp2-9VeeB6xp0HlvBEoFxr1rF8LJeHFv4vFwb7cviBw_54KU0bRsu4Q)
2. JAYDIP DATTA, THE TRENDS OF MODERN PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY: A DISCLOSURE, April 2020 , DOI: [10.6084/m9.figshare.12263126](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12263126)
(<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340579762> THE TRENDS OF MODERN PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY A DISCLOSURE? sg=9TnvBzR_EnTTc52y-GxlwGGtnEdlRdUuBY0kjLCz6TL6e-Ey_Id7a5i-Dnk9sqYz9y56Woappl25r4LnZwfytrRFwDnTjQmu3Ypf3q7.F2B-Rtmo7CBALLtnYPIKtEggxxwHQ5s4KHEbP161GPGqcrFcQ6nvXIPi4Gp0u9cPKSthOzeGW7SmdAwBt9a_qg)
3. JAYDIP DATTA, WAVE FUNCTION TO PARTITION FUNCTION: A CORRELATION, March 2021, DOI: [10.31219/osf.io/m9dzb](https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9dzb) (<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335401275> WAVE FUNCTION TO PARTITION FUNCTION A CORRELATION? sg=Hd44ZvcTSU7Kj38-B-Tife0R9YRQgR9cXk_nax1lhviQ5-VmToCTAdbipdATP0fVoXF1qNCmnNTkSIKng6HBlT3Zz2EEJZfol7CcqQha.of1-YVHX9enXZrpNYZ-9no7kKFW3ypWzClt4qm45z-9BBCPNJUJZhdhdQCulsO_MOO0gpvFuK1JdyaCwSedNfw)
4. JAYDIP DATTA , A SEMINAR ON PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY TEACHING - SOME

HIGHLIGHTS, October 2024 , DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.19024.46082/4](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19024.46082/4).

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334327584> A SEMINAR ON PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY TEACHING - SOME HIGHLIGHTS? sg%5B0%5D=EX4fenjeknz0gUBI7zDjRKCEyMODi1vTaDMwtzrbF0QKd9iv2TI7TaHsLNzS9giY-2QfYsFvA-a_D63B8PkVftbNohUXQwT6OFdBmC4W.LZBIZoXidulhilLPCubdrSzOWP3_gjHyPmtcAawTo-

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